

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397

p-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 5

ECHOES

of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

MAY 2026
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 5

ECHOES of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

Echoes of Expression
A Creative Folio

Volume II, Issue V (May 2026), National Circulation
ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741
Published Online at www.lakbay-diwapublishing.com
Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

Junry O. Villarba, MA

Instructor III

Jose Rizal Memorial State University - Siocon Campus
Siocon, Zamboanga del Norte, Philippines
DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20396565

Dreams Derailed by Becoming a Young Father

I was born from a family of poverty,
Once I dreamed,
Once I waited for miracles to find me,
Yet escaping hardship was never easy.

A chance came for me to study,
I entered the university through God's mercy,
I struggled and tried with all my might,
But the world lured me astray
And at a tender age, I became a father overnight.

Slowly, my dreams began to fade,
My parents carried sorrow in their hearts,
I ask myself if those dreams
Can still be reached someday,
Now that every thought I hold
Belongs to my child alone.

Forgive me, my father and mother,
I was carried away by a deceiving society,
The dreams we once built together
May never stand as they used to be,
For I became a young father
Far too early in life.